

1st Call for Papers

International Workshop on SMR Safety for a Sustainable Short-term Deployment

IRSN Headquarters, 31 av. De la Division Leclerc, Fontenay-aux-Roses, France
October 17th – 18th, 2024

The SASPAM-SA open workshop will promote international exchange of information and practices related to light water SMR safety considering the outcomes from the current ongoing Horizon Euratom SASPAM-SA project, other EU-Projects and other international initiatives (e.g. European SMR Pre-partnership, IAEA, OECD/NEA, ETSO, etc.). The workshop's objective is to share the advancements of the current major research activities on light water SMR safety and give the opportunity to discuss the main results. This allows to identify the needed knowledge development, in the view of additional short-term research actions, to support the SMR European licensing process.

TECHNICAL BACKGROUND

Nowadays light water cooled Small Modular Reactors (LW-SMR) are one of the key design options for the near-term deployment of nuclear reactor technology due to their generally recognized advantages (inherent safety, design simplicity, possibility of simplified batch production, reduction of construction time, capital and operational cost, etc.) and to their level of technological and licensing readiness.

The technological and licensing readiness of these designs is because LW-SMR starts from the well-proven-established operating large-Light Water Reactor (LWR) technology, incorporates their operational plant experience/feedback, and includes moderate evolutionary design modifications to increase the inherent safety of the plant. Therefore, it is envisaged to benefit from the operating large-LWR knowledge and know-how as a base of the SMR technology, minimizing the technological risks connected with innovative technological solutions proposed in innovative SMRs (that differ significantly from existing operating reactors). Therefore, several LW-SMR concepts are in advanced design state and ready to be licensed. Construction and certification activities are currently on-going and are expected to further increase and accelerate.

Considering the Net Zero Goal by 2050 in Europe, nuclear energy will have a key role in reaching this target with the aim of contributing to decarbonization in Europe. In the view of the envisaged short-term license process in European countries, a R&D program consistent with the European market needs and license requirements is in progress to ensure the implementation of the highest nuclear safety standards. In this regard, the safety demonstration is the key action to confirm the adequacy of the safety provisions ensuring the stable and safe operation of an SMR in all the plant states. Within this framework, [Euratom Research and Training Programs](#) have a key role in supporting R&D activities, speeding-up licensing process, and securing a leading position for European Initiatives within the international framework. European projects are articulated addressing different topics, in order to support the expected safety demonstration of SMR in Europe, and different actions are in progress or have been recently finished (e.g. [ELSMOR](#), [HARMONISE](#), [MCSAFER](#), [PASTELS](#), [SASPAM-SA](#), [TANDEM](#)).

Considering the outcomes from the current on-going Horizon Euratom SASPAM-SA project (organizer of this event) as well as from the other European projects already finished or currently ongoing, as well as other international initiatives ([European SMR Pre-partnership](#), [IAEA](#), [OECD/NEA](#), [ETSON](#), etc.), the workshop objective is to carry out a state-of-art to identify remaining knowledge gaps linked to the safety demonstration of LW-SMR. The workshop will offer the opportunity to identify the current gaps and how to address them with short-term additional research actions.

SCOPE AND TECHNICAL CONTENT OF THE WORKSHOP

The scope considers the safety demonstration of LW-SMRs and the related aspects. Therefore, the focus of the Workshop is to discuss and review the state-of-art and the needed knowledge development on:

- Accident scenarios in LW-SMRs and related phenomenology;
- Capabilities of safety computer codes to predict LW-SMR phenomenology in transient conditions;
- Applicability of existing experimental database to characterize LW-SMR phenomenology in steady-operational and transient conditions;
- Analyses of the current severe accident mitigation strategies and features (e.g. IVMR, hydrogen management) and related modeling aspects;
- Computer code guidelines and best practices for the simulation of LW-SMR;
- Applicability of tools and methods to determine the emergency planning zone (EPZ) for LW-SMR;
- Applicability of high-fidelity tools for the safety analysis of LW-SMRs;
- Safety of LW-SMR integrated into a hybrid energy systems;
- Safety research in standardization and nuclear safety.

OUTCOMES OF THE WORKSHOP

SASPAM-SA open workshop aims to create a platform to specifically discuss about the safety of LW-SMRs in the view of a sustainable short-term deployment. The workshop will be a thematic platform to share with the participants the current advancements on SMR safety. In addition, the applicability of the operating large-LWR reactor knowledge and know-how to the near-term deployment of LW-SMR will be presented, in the view of licensing analysis needs in Europe regarding severe accident and EPZ. Key outcomes of the workshop will be:

- Provide an overview of the progress made in the SASPAM-SA project;
- Bring together EU-projects dealing with the safety of light water cooled SMR;
- Bring together the main activities related to the safety of the light water cooled SMR at international level;
- Discuss safety issues inherent to LW-SMRs, including coupling with industrial facilities, and how to address them;
- Identify potential remaining safety issues to be investigated;
- Foster coordination among international activities.

ORGANIZING COMMITTEE

The technical content of the workshop has been prepared by the Organizing Committee members:

Ahmed BENTAIB	IRSN	France
Fulvio MASCARI	ENEA	Italy
Fabrizio GABRIELLI	KIT	Germany
Terttaliisa LIND	PSI	Switzerland
Florian FICHOT	IRSN	France
Nils REINKE	GRS	Germany
Mikko ILVONEN	VTT	Finland
Fabio GIANNETTI	UNI ROMA	Italy

SCIENTIFIC COMMITTEE (ON-GOING)

Sanjeev GUPTA	Becker Technologies GmbH	Germany
Claire VAGLIO-GAUDARD	CEA	France
Luis Enrique HERRANZ	CIEMAT	Spain
Andrew MORREALE	CNL	Canada
Mounia BERDAI	CNSC	Canada
Michael MONTOUT	EDF	France
Sylvain TAKENOUTI	EDF	France
Fulvio MASCARI	ENEA	Italy
Ahmed BENTAIB	IRSN	France
Sebastien ISRAEL	IRSN	France
Victor SANCHEZ	KIT	Germany
Egidijus URBONAVICIUS	LEI	Lithuania
Hideo NAKAMURA	JAEA	Japan
Martina ADORNI	OECD/NEA	France
Dave LUXAT	SNL	USA
Tereza Abrman MARKOVÁ	SUJB	Czech Republic
Shawn CAMPBELL	USNRC	USA
Ville TULKKI	VTT	Finland

PROCEEDINGS AND SUMMARY REPORT

The proceedings of the workshop will include the presentations, the extended abstracts and the conclusions summary. Possible special issue in a Journal.

CONTACT PERSONS

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PARTICIPATION AND EXTENDED ABSTRACT SUBMISSION

The SASPAM-SA workshop “International Workshop on SMR Safety for a Sustainable Short-term Deployment” is intended for participants from Regulators, TSO, Universities, Research centers, Industries, Operators, International Agency, Emergency responders, Code developers, Code users, SA analysts, iPWR analysts, Experimentalists. The organizing committee is exploring possible remote participation in case of any remaining COVID-19 travel restriction. Authors are required to submit extended abstracts in English addressing the scope of the workshop, by e-mail to: SASPAM_WS_SMR_SAFETY@irsn.fr

Submission:

- Instructions for Extended Abstract preparation appear in the last page and the template is available at the workshop website: [SASPAM-SA / International Open Workshop – SASPAM-SA](https://www.irsn.fr/~/media/IRSN/Document/2023/06/SASPAM-SA_International_Open_Workshop_-_SASPAM-SA_(ongoing).pdf) (ongoing)
- Notification of abstract acceptance by email;
- Extended Abstract will be reviewed by the Scientific Committee;
- Oral and posters sessions can be envisaged;
- Selected papers will be encouraged for publication in technical journals.

ATTENTION PLEASE:

Important dates:

Extended Abstract submission: May 31th, 2024
 Notification of Abstract acceptance: June 30th, 2024
 Final Extended Abstract submission: September 30th, 2024

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